

Cognitive, emotional and somatosensory behavior in professional dancers with acute and chronic pain

Running title: Dancers and pain behavior

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Conflicts of Interest Statement

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Dance has been linked in a complex manner to pain and the physical and psychological peculiarities of this discipline could influence pain perception and chronicity of pain.

Objective: To determine the differences in cognitive, emotional, and somatosensory symptoms between dancers with acute versus chronic pain.

Design: A cross sectional study of professional dancers with pain

Setting: Higher Conservatory of Dance

Participants: 34 professional dancers experiencing pain were included. The cohort was divided into two subgroups: those with acute pain (< 3 months duration) and those with chronic pain (> 3 months duration).

Interventions: Not applicable

Main Outcome Measures: Pain intensity (as measured by the visual analogue scale or VAS), pressure pain threshold (PPT), pain catastrophizing scale (PCS), pain-related fear of movement (TSK-11), fear avoidance beliefs (FAB-Q), self-efficacy (CPSS) and chronic pain severity (CPGS)

Results: Dancers with CP reported higher levels of pain intensity in daily activities ($p < 0.01$; $t = 3.42$; $d = 1.17$) and during exercise/dance ($p = 0.02$; $t = 2.82$; $d = 0.82$), as well as lower PPT in lumbar ($p = 0.03$; $t = 3.22$; $d = 1.1$) and tibialis regions ($p = 0.01$; $t = 2.51$; $d = 0.86$). Dancers with AP dancers experienced worse psychological symptoms including fear of harm subscale of TSK-11 ($p = 0.04$; $t = -2.08$; $d = 0.72$), physical activity subscale of FABQ ($p = 0.03$; $t = -2.27$; $d = 0.78$), pain management subscale of CPSS ($p = 0.01$; $t = -2.76$; $d = 0.94$); and lower scores for CPGS scale ($p = 0.01$; $t = 2.99$; $d = 0.7$ to 1.26).

Conclusions: The results showed differences in pain intensity and PPT revealing higher values in dancers with chronic pain. It is possible that the physical and psychological characteristics of dancers, as well as the socio-cultural aspects of this discipline, could influence the way in which this population interprets pain.

Keywords: Dancers; Chronic Pain; Acute Pain; Pain behavior.

INTRODUCTION

Dance is the result of the union between scenic art and sport and is physically, psychologically, and aesthetically demanding.¹ Since ancient times, this discipline has been linked in a complex manner to pain, and there is a cultural expectation that dancers experience or should experience pain.² Dancers have a high prevalence of individuals with acute and chronic pain (defined as pain that persists beyond the typical tissue recovery time or > 3 months),³ predominantly in body regions exposed to high mechanical stress specific to dance.⁴ There has been a significant increase in research related to chronic pain, where important structural and functional changes of the brain as central sensitization processes in individuals with chronic pain have been observed.⁵ This has led to the development of new hypotheses on the functioning of pain and to the beginning of its analysis from a biopsychosocial approach, in which sensory, emotional, cognitive, and social components are associated.⁶ Previous studies determine that pain chronicity could be related to a processing alteration at the central nervous system.⁷ Neuroplastic changes at the medullary and supramedullary level may influence pain perception.⁷

There are also several psychological variables related to the perception and emotional management of pain including catastrophizing, self-efficacy, and fear-avoidance behaviors, that have been shown to be related to the development of chronic pain.^{5, 8} Psychosocial factors should be considered, since the cognitions, emotions, and behaviors related to the emotions of the athlete are associated with the rehabilitation outcomes.⁹ However, there is little published related to psychological factors associated with chronic pain in dancers.

Although the pain intensity perceived by professional dancers is highly variable between different studies, some of them have shown that more than 60% of professional dancers report pain of moderate or severe intensity.^{1,12} In addition, compared to non-dancers, it suggests that non-dancers have a greater pain perception, although pain tolerance is higher in professional dancers.¹³ In this regard, a meta-analysis showed that athletes, including dancers, have a higher threshold tolerance for pressure pain compared to non-athletes.¹⁴ However, and despite the high prevalence of pain in dancers, no study to date has evaluated the physical and psychological peculiarities of this discipline, and its association with pain perception and chronicity of pain.

The neurophysiological changes underlying the chronification of pain, as well as the socio-cultural, emotional, and cognitive particularities of this discipline could produce different somatosensory and psychological alterations. Therefore, our primary aim was to determine the differences between cognitive, emotional, and somatosensory variables among dancers with acute and chronic pain. The secondary aim was to determine the differences between somatosensory and psychological variables among dancers classified according to their pain intensity level. Thus, we hypothesize that the chronicity of pain and pain intensity could alter pain perception levels in professional athletes.

METHODS

Study design

A cross-sectional study design with a non-probabilistic sample was used. The design followed the international recommendations for Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE).¹⁵ All participants received an explanation of the study procedures, which were planned according to the ethical standards of the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by an Ethics Committee. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants before their inclusion.

Participants

A non-probabilistic sample of professional dancers was recruited between February 2019 and May 2019 from a Higher Conservatory of Dance. Participants were divided into two groups based on the duration of their pain: acute pain (AP) if pain duration was less than 3 months or chronic pain (CP) if pain duration was more than 3 months.

The inclusion criteria were the following: a) Professional dancers; b) Men or women between 18 and 45 years; c) understanding of the Spanish language; d) presence of musculoskeletal pain of less than 3 months' duration (AP group) or presence of musculoskeletal pain of more than 3 months' duration (CP group).

Exclusion criteria for both groups were: a) injured dancers without current professional activity; b) having previously participated in a similar study that could influence participant expectations; c) presence of vestibular, ocular, or postural deficiencies; d) unable to understand instructions in Spanish; or e) autoimmune or neurological diseases that could influence the measurement variables.

Outcomes

Pain intensity

A Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) was used to measure pain intensity levels. VAS is a 100-mm line with two endpoints representing the extreme states “no pain” (0mm) and “the maximal pain imaginable” (100mm). It has been shown to have good reliability (ICC= 0.97 [95% CI = 0.96 to 0.98]).¹⁶ VAS was assessed during daily live activities (VAS activity) and during exercise/dance (VAS exercise).

Somatosensory variables

Pressure Pain Threshold (PPT): The pain threshold to pressure is a widely used method to quantify the tissue sensitivity. As a standard, the pain detection threshold is defined as the minimum pressure that must be applied to cause a first painful sensation.

PPTs were measured using a Wagner digital algometer (FPX 25 Wagner Instruments, Greenwich, CT, USA) equipped with a 1 cm² rubber head. A perpendicular force over the anatomical zone to be measured was applied with the algometer, and continuously increased at a speed of 1Kg per second following Fisher's protocol.¹⁷ When the participant experienced discomfort or pain, the researcher stopped the test, registering the strength in kg marked on the instrument. Each measurement was repeated a total of three times per anatomical area, from which a mean was extracted. This measure showed good reliability (ICC 0.94 to 0.96).¹⁸

The points measured were upper trapezium, lumbar paravertebral, short radial carpal extender, and tibialis anterior. For the upper trapezium, the researcher performed a pass with slight digital pressure from the acromion insertion to the portion of the muscle closest to the spine, choosing the point of maximum sensitivity.¹⁹ In the case of the lumbar, the researcher performed a pass with slight digital pressure, in the cranio-flow direction, on the paravertebral muscles that coincided with the levels from T12 to L5, choosing the point of maximum sensitivity.²⁰ In the case of the forearm, the examiner differentiated the belly from the brachioradial muscle and the common extensor of the fingers, applying the same discriminating palpation, in a cranio-flow direction, between the two muscular bellies.²¹ Finally, the examiner carried out the same palpation at the level of the tibialis anterior, starting from a finger to the side of the tibialis tuberosity and descending in a cranio-feeding direction along the belly of the tibialis anterior.¹⁹ All points were measured bilaterally following the same protocol.

Cognitive and emotional variables

Pain catastrophizing: The Spanish version of the Pain Catastrophizing Scale (PCS) assesses the degree of pain catastrophizing. It has been demonstrated as having acceptable psychometric properties for the Spanish version (Cronbach's alpha: 0.79). The PCS has

13 items and a three-factor structure: rumination subscale, magnification subscale, and helplessness subscale. Higher scores indicate more catastrophizing. The final score can range between 0 and 52, and higher scores represent higher levels of pain catastrophizing.²²

Pain-related fear of movement: Pain-related fear of movement was assessed using the 11-item Spanish version of the Tampa Scale for Kinesiophobia, whose reliability and validity have been demonstrated (Cronbach's alpha of 0.79).²³ The Tampa Scale for Kinesiophobia consists of two subscales, one related to fear of activity and the other related to fear of harm. The final score can range between 11 and 44 points, with higher scores indicating greater perceived kinesiophobia.²³

Fear-avoidance beliefs: The Fear-Avoidance Beliefs Questionnaire has proven to be understandable and reliable, for measuring avoidance fear behaviors in patients with chronic pain.²⁴ This tool consists of 16 items, the first 5 on pain response to physical activity (FABQ physical activity subscale) and the next on how work affects pain (FABQ work subscale). The response is variable 0-6 (I totally disagree - I completely agree). Thus, the higher the score, the greater the fear-avoidance component.

Self-efficacy: The Spanish version of the Chronic Pain Self-Efficacy Scale (CPSS) has been demonstrated as having acceptable psychometric properties in assessing the perceived Self-Efficacy (SE) and ability to cope with the consequences of chronic pain. The CPSS consists of 19 items and three domains that assess SE for pain management (PSE), physical function (FSE), and coping with symptoms (SSE). Higher scores indicating greater SE for managing pain.²⁵ The CPSS presented reliability of 0.88, 0.87, and 0.90 for PSE, FSE, and SSE, respectively.²⁵

Chronic pain severity: The chronic pain grading scale (CPGS) has proven to be a reliable tool for determining the magnitude of chronic pain. This scale was validated in Spanish

with patients with chronic low-back pain, demonstrating an internal consistency value of 0.87.²⁶ It consists of 8 items in 11-point Likert format with a total range of 0-70 points. The score was calculated for 3 subscales: the characteristic pain intensity score, the disability score, and the disability points score. Thus, a higher score represents greater severity of chronic pain.

Baseline variables

Physical activity level: The level of physical activity was objectified through the International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ), which allows the participants to be divided into three groups according to their level of activity: high, moderate, and low or inactive. This questionnaire has shown acceptable validity and psychometric properties to measure total physical activity. We used the short version, which consists of 7 items that measure the participant's overall level of physical activity in the last 7 days.²⁷

Sample size calculation

A pilot study was carried out with 8 subjects per group, analyzing the data of the PPT variable using a Student t, an effect size of 0.9 was extracted. The sample size was calculated using the G * Power 3.1.9.2 program for Mac (G * Power©), to detect differences between the 2 groups with the Student t statistical test for independent samples, using a statistical power of 80% (1- β error probability) with an error level probability α of 0.05. This has generated a total sample size of 32 subjects, having 16 subjects per group.

Procedure

For this study, both groups performed the same procedure following the same instructions. The assessor was blinded for the participants' allocation. Once the participants signed the informed consent, the subjects received a sociodemographic questionnaire, which collected gender, date of birth, education level, and work situation.

In addition, physical activity levels were assessed using the IPAQ.²⁸ Following, the subjects completed all four psychological questionnaires with an invariable order across the participants. Following the completion of the self-reported measures, the PPT where measured.

Statistical Analysis

The sociodemographic and clinical variables of the participants were analyzed. The data were summarized using frequency counts, descriptive statistics, summary tables, and figures. Participants were divided according to their pain chronicity for the primary analysis (AP and CP groups based on pain duration of 3 months) and based on the pain intensity score (CPGS) for secondary analysis. Median for this variable was calculated and participants were distributed according they had more or less punctuation concerning the median.

The data analysis was performed using the Statistics Package for Social Science (SPSS 20.00, IBM Inc., USA). The categorical variables are shown as frequency and percentage. The quantitative results of the study are represented by descriptive statistics (confidence interval [CI], mean, and standard deviation [SD]). The normality of the variables was assessed with the Shapiro-Wilk test. The Student T-test was used for the group comparisons. Cohen's *d* effect sizes were calculated for multiple comparisons of the outcome variables. According to Cohen's method, the magnitude of the effect was classified as small (<0.20-0.49), medium (0.50-0.79), or large (≥ 0.80).

RESULTS

Forty professional dancers were screened, and finally, 34 subjects were included in the study (four subjects were excluded for having had surgery and two subjects for having autoimmune diseases).

Primary analysis: Chronicity of pain

Participants were divided into two groups based on the pain duration: AP group and CP group **Table 1** shows the results of demographic variables. Only statistically significant differences were observed in age ($p=0.02$). The remaining variables did not show significant statistically differences. On the other hand, the Chi Square test did not show statistically significant differences in the qualitative variables ($p>0.05$).

Pain intensity

Results showed statistically significant differences in pain intensity during daily activity ($p<0.01$; $t=3.42$; $d=1.17$) and during exercise/dance ($p=0.02$; $t=2.82$; $d=0.82$), with higher levels for the CP group in both variables (**Table 2 and Figure 1**).

Somatosensory variables

Regarding somatosensory variables, results showed statistically significant differences in lumbar ($p=0.03$; $t=3.22$; $d=1.1$) and tibialis ($p=0.01$; $t=2.51$; $d=0.86$) PTT regions, with lower levels for the CP group in both variables (**Table 2 and Figure 2**).

Cognitive and emotional variables

Regarding psychological variables, AP group showed higher statistically significant differences for physical activity subscale of FABQ ($p=0.03$; $t=-2.27$; $d=0.78$), fear of harm subscale of TSK-11 ($p=0.04$; $t=-2.08$; $d=0.72$) and pain management subscale of CPSS ($p=0.01$; $t=-2.76$; $d=0.94$). In addition, significant differences were found in total CPGS scale ($p=0.01$; $t=2.99$; $d=0.94$), as well as in the intensity score ($p=0.01$; $t=3.67$; $d=1.26$) and disability score ($p=0.04$; $t=2.04$; $d=0.7$), with higher values for CP group (**Table 3**).

Secondary analysis: Pain intensity

For this analysis, the participants were divided according to the results obtained in the intensity score subscale of the CPGS. The median was calculated for this variable (median=16) and the subjects were divided according to this: lower pain intensity levels (LP group; n=17) and higher pain intensity levels (HP group; n=17).

Somatosensory variables

Results did not show any statistically significant differences for PPT between LP and HP groups.

Cognitive and emotional variables

Results did not show any statistically significant differences for PCS, TSK-11, CPSS, CPGS test between LP and HP groups.

DISCUSSION

The primary objective was to determine differences between somatosensory, cognitive, and emotional variables among dancers with acute and chronic pain. The results showed differences in pain intensity, revealing higher values in the CP group. Concerning somatosensory variables, differences were found in PPT. In addition, AP group presented higher levels of fear-avoidance beliefs regarding physical activity in the FABQ questionnaire, as well as fear of harm in the TSK-11 scale and self-efficacy for pain management.

Pain perception in dancers is largely influenced by multiple factors, including the complex sensory-motor aspects of this discipline, which could be affected by the presence of chronic pain.¹ Currently, pain is defined as a perceptual inference modulated by affective-emotional and cognitive- evaluative factors, that attempt to protect the individual from actual or potential harm. In this sense, movement is widely linked to the

pain presence.²⁹ Previous research has shown that pain directly influences movement, and individuals with pain move differently than individuals without pain.³⁰ Since the complex movement and the competitive requirements of the dance movements, pain could be a critical variable in this population. Pain could affect dance movements both from a proprioceptive perspective and in planning and movement execution terms at the central nervous system level.³¹

In addition, chronic pain may have a direct influence on cortical body representation. Cortical representation integrates information in somatosensory areas about the body and the stimuli it receives. Somatosensory stimuli altered by the pain presence influence cortical representation, and our results may reflect that disturbance.³² Somatosensory disorders may also be related to higher chronic pain prevalence, especially in the lower back and lower limb, found previously in this population.³³ Additionally, it has been shown that subjects with chronic pain exhibit impairments in the endogenous pain modulation systems, which could lead to increased neuronal response and greater pain perception.³⁴

It is also necessary to highlight that emotional and cognitive factors could modulate central motor and sensory responses.³⁵ Pain beliefs may play a role in pain perception. Traditionally, in dance science, two types of pain are identified. First, a pain associated with performance and activity itself, which is traditionally considered normal, with a less dangerous character. Second, there is the pain of injury, associated with real health risk and which limits the execution of the dance activity.^{36,37} Previously, it has been described that the pain associated with an injury is perceived with greater intensity by dancers.³⁷ However, on several occasions pain is perceived as a necessity of the discipline itself, so it is often ignored. This socio-cultural aspect of dance means that usually, the way to manage pain is to accept it and ignore it.³⁸ Pain normalization behavior may be related

to the lower presence of psychological variables found in CP group. In this sense, a previous study found that less experienced dancers have higher levels of fear-avoidance or catastrophism factors compared to more experienced dancers.^{37,39}

Dancers with chronic pain may perceive pain less threateningly and keep their physical activity levels high, extinguishing beliefs of fear avoidance. In other populations with pain, physical activity levels have previously been associated with fear-avoidance beliefs.^{40,41} However, acceptance behavior could represent a risk to dancers, as it is considered a risk factor for possible injury or chronicity of pain.³⁰ Although in other populations the pain duration does not seem to be a determining factor, socio-cultural factors specific to dancers and the high physical and psychological demand for dance may influence pain duration as a critical factor at the somatosensory or psychological level. This may also be related to the results obtained in our secondary analysis, in which no significant differences in somatosensory or psychological variables are observed between dancers with higher and lower pain intensity.

This study presents novel data about the dancers' pain behavior. The distinctive socio-cultural characteristics of this sport, as well as the peculiarities in the physical and psychological requirements of the dancers, could significantly affect the beliefs and behaviors of dancers. Due to the high pain prevalence in dancers, it is essential to understand how acute and chronic pain can affect the somatosensory and psychological aspects of this population. These data may provide important information in the understanding of dancers for sport sciences and rehabilitation, which could lead to the development of better assessment and treatment programs.

Limitations

This study presents some limitations that should be taken into account in the interpretation of the results. Firstly, the differences found in the variables age and gender could have

relevance in the results obtained. Secondly, the difficulty in finding painless dancers impeded the inclusion of a control group of painless dancers. Thirdly, the differences between the different pain locations could influence the psychological and somatosensory variables measured in the present research. Fourth, pain duration was evaluated as a categorical variable, so it was not possible to establish associations between pain duration and somatosensory, emotional, or cognitive variables. Finally, the sample was nonprobabilistic and recruited by convenience, which could represent a bias in the results.

CONCLUSIONS

The results showed differences in cognitive, emotional, and somatosensory between AP and CP dancers. Pain intensity and PPT revealed higher values in dancers with CP but dancers with AP presented higher levels of fear-avoidance beliefs as well as fear of harm and self-efficacy.

It is possible that the physical and psychological characteristics of dancers, as well as the socio-cultural aspects of this discipline, could influence how this population interprets pain, which could influence somatosensory, cognitive, and emotional behavior and should be taken into account in the management of dancers with pain.

Conflicts of Interest Statement

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest. This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors

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FIGURE CAPTIONS

Figure 1. Results of pain intensity variable according pain chronicity analysis. VAS: Visual Analogue Scale; CP: Chronic Pain Group; AP: Acute Pain Group; *: $p < 0.05$; **: $p < 0.01$; $d =$ Effect size (Cohen d).

Figure 2. Results of somatosensory variables (pain pressure threshold) according pain chronicity analysis. PPT: Pain Pressure Threshold; CP: Chronic Pain Group; AP: Acute Pain Group; *: $p < 0.05$; **: $p < 0.01$; $d =$ Effect size (Cohen d).

Figure 1.

Figure 2.JPG

Table 1. Descriptive, demographic data and control variables.

	CP (n=17)	AP (n=17)	p value
Age (years)	25 ± 5.350	21.58 ± 2.575	0.02
BMI (kg/m²)	21.06 ± 1.987	20.66 ± 1.441	0.51
Years of training	15.65 ± 4.358	14 ± 3.953	0.26
Hours of training	29.44 ± 10.718	27.88 ± 6.679	0.61
Physical activity (METs)	9137.12 ± 2840.077	8064 ± 1810.153	0.2
Gender			
- Men	3 (17.6)	3 (17.6)	0.89
- Women	14 (82.4)	14 (82.4)	
Dance style			
- Classic	4 (23.5)	5 (29.4)	
- Contemporary	7 (41.2)	7 (41.2)	0.9
- Spanish	6 (35.3)	5 (29.4)	
Lumbopelvic pain	11 (64.7)	8 (47.1)	0.3
Knee pain	8 (47.1)	3 (17.6)	0.07
Foot pain	7 (41.2)	6 (35.3)	0.72
Spinal pain	13 (76.5)	9 (52.9)	0.15
Upper limb pain	2 (11.8)	0 (0)	0.15

BMI: Body Mass index; AP: Acute pain group; CP: Chronic pain group.

Table 2. Comparative data of the sample of pain intensity and somatosensory variables

	CP (n=17)	AP (n=17)	Mean Difference (95% CI); Effect size (<i>d</i> Cohen)
VAS Activity	4.42 ± 1.669	2.64 ± 1.345	1.78** (0.72 to 2.84); <i>d</i> = 1.17
VAS Exercise/dance	4.61 ± 2.097	3.02 ± 1.766	1.59* (0.23 to 2.94); <i>d</i> = 0.82
Pressure Pain Thresholds			
Neck region	3.56 ± 1.52	4.19 ± 1.41	-0.63 (-1.65 to 0.4); <i>d</i> = -0.43
Lumbar region	8.3 ± 2.6	11.73 ± 3.53	-3.43* (-5.61 to -1.27); <i>d</i> = -1.1
Forearm region	4.92 ± 1.99	5.9 ± 1.63	-0.98 (-2.25 to 0.29); <i>d</i> =-0.53
Tibialis region	8.59 ± 2.89	11.85 ± 4.49	-3.27* (-5.91 to -0.62); <i>d</i> =-0.86

p*< 0.05; *p*<0.01; AP: Acute pain group; CP: Chronic pain group; VAS: Visual Analogue Scale

Table 3. Comparative data of the sample of psychological variables

	CP (n=17)	AP (n=17)	Mean Difference (95% CI); Effect Size (<i>d</i> Cohen)
PCS			
PCS-R	5.24 ± 2.905	5.06 ± 3.01	0.18 (-1.89 a 2.24); <i>d</i> =0.06
PCS-M	4.29 ± 1.929	3.76 ± 2.538	0.53 (-1.05 a 2.1); <i>d</i> =0.23
PCS-H	6.41 ± 3.858	4.35 ± 3.9	2.06 (-0.65 a 4.77); <i>d</i> =0.53
TSK-11			
TSK-AA	12.18 ± 2.984	10.65 ± 3.499	1.53 (-0.74 a 3.8); <i>d</i> =0.47
TSK-H	7.88 ± 2.088	9.59 ± 2.647	-1.71* (-3.37 a -0.04) <i>d</i> =-0.72
FAB-Q			
FABQ-W	15.71 ± 6.06	19.65 ± 3.823	-3.94* (-7.48 a -0.4); <i>d</i> =-0.78
FABQ-PA	19.53 ± 10.131	19.88 ± 9.327	-0.35 (-7.16 a 6.45); <i>d</i> =-0.04
CPSS			
CPSS-SSE	60.05 ± 9.896	61.35 ± 8.602	-1.29 (-7.77 a 5.18); <i>d</i> =-0.14
CPSS-FSE	56.24 ± 3.817	55.53 ± 4.502	0.71 (-2.21 a 3.62); <i>d</i> =0.17
CPSS-PSE	33.59 ± 8.917	40.82 ± 6.147	-7.24* (-12.59 a -1.89); <i>d</i> =-0.94
CPGS			
CPGS-DS	14.76 ± 9.11	9.23 ± 6.38	5.53* (0.03 to 11.02); <i>d</i> =0.70
CPGS-IS	19.71 ± 5.08	13.76 ± 4.32	5.94* (2.64 to 9.24); <i>d</i> =1.26
CPGS	100.17 ± 58.37	54.17 ± 37.71	46* (11.66 to 80.33); <i>d</i> =0.94

* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; AP: Acute pain group; CP: Chronic pain group; PCS: Pain Catastrophizing Scale; PCS-R: Pain Catastrophizing Scale-Rumination Subscale; PCS-M: Pain Catastrophizing Scale-Magnification Subscale; PCS-H: Pain Catastrophizing Scale- Helplessness Subscale TSK-11: Tampa Scale of Kinesiophobia; TSK-AA: Tampa Scale of Kinesiophobia-Activity Avoidance subscale; TSK-H: Tampa Scale of Kinesiophobia- Harm subscale; FAB-Q: Fear Avoidance Beliefs Questionnaire; FABQ-W: Fear Avoidance Beliefs Questionnaire-Work Subscale; FABQ-PA: Fear Avoidance Beliefs Questionnaire- Physical Activity Subscale; CPSS: Chronic Pain Self-Efficacy Scale; CPSS-SSE: Chronic Pain Self-Efficacy Scale-Coping with symptoms subscale; CPSS-FSE: Chronic Pain Self-Efficacy Scale- Physical Function subscale; CPSS-PSE: Chronic Pain Self-Efficacy Scale-Pain management subscale; CPGS: Chronic Pain Graded Scale; CPGS-DS: Chronic Pain Graded Scale-Disability score; CPGS-IS: Chronic Pain Graded Scale-Intensity Score;